

TURKISH ADAPTATION OF STUDY-LEISURE CONFLICT SCALE, ITS VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

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Abstract:

This study aimed to adapt to Turkish the measurement of work-leisure conflict developed by Tsaur et al. (2012) to measure work-leisure conflict and to present the causes and dimensions of the conflict and to develop a new study-leisure conflict scale for university students based on the items of this scale and to undertake reliability and validity studies for the new measure. A total of 306 students took part in the study. First of all, "Measurement of Work-Leisure", the foundation for this study, was translated into Turkish in order to ensure linguistic equivalence. Validity was investigated by using explanatory and confirmatory factor analyses. Reliability was calculated by utilizing Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient, split halves method and Guttman reliability coefficient. Statistical results obtained from the study show that the adapted Turkish version of the scale was a valid and reliable measurement instrument.

Keywords: study-leisure conflict, scale development, validity, reliability

1. Introduction

Individuals' need for leisure has started to take precedence over their regular daily activities. Leisure activities are a part of individuals' lives now and they are mentioned and associated with the individuals who pursue them. This approach causes conflicts between leisure activities and responsibilities of daily life. Daily activities are defined as the activities that individuals are obliged to do in order to continue their work or study lives or their existence in general. For adults, daily activities include working and earning income while they comprise of attending school and obtaining high grades from courses for students. Leisure is known to exist since agricultural societies. In terms of work/leisure, history of humanity is devoted to survival activities whereas leisure activities involve a few hours that remain from the time dedicated to meet the relatively

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basic needs (Steppins; 2012). Work in this context means activities that are compulsory for individuals to complete during the course of a day. However, in modern societies, compulsory activities have been diversified and are different for each individual. While an activity may be regarded as work for one person, it may be a leisure activity for another. Also, whereas a leisure activity may be a mere activity for the individual for a time, it can transform into work by time. When it is considered that leisure activities are more fun compared to work or study, it will be seen that these two concepts appear as problems since they are in conflict and they obstruct each other to a certain extent (Isik, 2014). In this context, the meaning of leisure changes from individual to individual. In their study, Gürbüz and Henderson (2013) found that university students defined leisure using different definitions such as perceived freedom (e.g. to do what one wants, to feel free to use time), relation to work (e.g. to do something different from daily duties) or social interaction (e.g. to meet other people, to be in touch with other people). It is apparent that the meaning of leisure changes from person to person.

In recent years, many studies have investigated work-leisure and family-leisure conflict (Guttek et al., 1991; Carlson et al., 2000; Lobo, 2006; Zhao & Rashid, 2010). Researchers first studied the conflict between work and family life. Work-family conflict is based on the conflict of work roles and family roles and is the reflection of work related pressures to family life (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). For instance, an individual with a decision making position at work may tend to continue decision making behaviors in family life as well. Also, work-leisure conflict, which is centered on work-family conflict, has similar characteristics. Many theoretical and empirical studies have investigated this field since 1970s. All studies in the field point that the topic can be studied from two aspects. The first aspect is related to conflict due to work interfering with leisure and the other aspect is related to conflict due to leisure interfering with work. More explicitly, when an individual tries to spend more time on leisure activities, he/she cannot concentrate on work (cannot spend time on work issues) or the stress resulting from the desire to achieve more in leisure activities reflect on work environment negatively. This situation may work in reverse as well: stress experienced during work cannot be overcome with leisure activities or sufficient time cannot be spared for leisure activities due to work load.

Need for leisure increases day by day in modern life. Especially school age children and university youth need leisure activities more. Studies conducted on these target groups show that the basic cause for school-leisure conflict is related to students' motivation levels for the leisure activities they are involved in and the quality of these leisure activities (Fries et al., 2008). These studies also focused on the causes for motivation and sought the foundations of motivation for making a preference between study and leisure activities. (Dietz et al., 2005; Ratelle et al., 2005; Senécal et al., 2003; Hofer et al., 2010). All these studies were empirical; students were provided with scenarios and asked how they would respond to these scenarios. A sample scenario used in Grund and Fries' (2012) study is provided below:

“You are sitting at your desk at home and getting ready to read a chapter to study for tomorrow’s class. At this moment, the phone rings. Your friend is calling to ask if you would join them to do something together outside. They want to pick you up from home in a few moments”.

Many studies investigating study-leisure conflict utilized similar scenarios and collected participant views to obtain results. Although there are scales to measure family-work or work-leisure conflicts, a scale that directly measures study-leisure conflict does not exist. Turkish literature does not have any scales that focus on measuring study-leisure conflict as well.

In this context, this study aimed to adapt to Turkish the measurement of work-leisure conflict developed by Tsaur et al. (2012) to measure work-leisure conflict and to present the causes and dimensions of the conflict and to develop a new study-leisure conflict scale for university students based on the items of this scale and to undertake reliability and validity studies for the new measure.

2. Method

2.1 Participants

Dumlupınar University students in Kutahya province participated in the study on a voluntary basis. A total of 306 students took part in the study (Mage=21,98; Ss.=2,80). Participants filled in the surveys in the classroom and they were reminded to ask for clarification on unclear points.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

The study utilized the “Study-Leisure Conflict Scale” prepared and revised by the researchers in line with “Measurement of Work-Leisure” developed by Tsaur et al., (2012). The original scale had 30 items and 6 sub scales that measure employees’ work-leisure conflicts. The terms in these 30 items related to work were changed with those related to school and instructions were changed so that some of the items could be better comprehended. 6 sub scales in the original survey are as follows: Time based WIL (Conflict due to work interfering with leisure), Strain-based WIL, Behavior based WIL, Time based LIW (Conflict due to leisure interfering with work), Strain based LIW, Behavior LIW. SPSS 21.0 and AMOS 22.0 programs were used in data analyses.

2.3 Procedure and Data Analysis

First of all, “Measurement of Work-Leisure”, the foundation for this study, was translated into Turkish in order to ensure linguistic equivalence. Validity was investigated by using explanatory and confirmatory factor analyses. Reliability was calculated by utilizing Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient, split halves method and Guttman reliability coefficient.

3. Findings

3.1 Linguistic equivalence

Translation process included specific phases. The original scale was translated to Turkish by 4 English instructors; the translated scale was assessed by 3 academicians with expertise in the field of recreation and the parts related to “work” was changed to “study” in accordance with the field of recreation and the characteristics that were aimed to be measured. The next step included revisions by 2 Turkish instructors to increase intelligibility. Later, 3 individuals other than the English instructors who translated the scale into Turkish translated the Turkish scale back into English. The difference between the original scale and the translated one was related to changes in the words “work-study” and experts reported no other differences. Then, 25 university students attending English Language and Literature were asked to fill the English and Turkish scales at two week intervals and the correlation between these two scales was used to complete the linguistic equivalence study.

Table 1: Findings related to linguistic equivalence of the scale

Factor	Treatment	X	Ss	r
Factor 1	Turkish Form	2,73	0,74	.90
	English Form	2,77	0,61	
Factor 2	Turkish Form	2,86	0,68	.82
	English Form	3,00	0,92	
Factor 3	Turkish Form	2,45	0,99	.80
	English Form	2,72	0,85	
Factor 4	Turkish Form	2,59	0,83	.85
	English Form	2,83	0,20	
Factor 5	Turkish Form	2,42	0,87	.79
	English Form	2,86	0,80	
Factor 6	Turkish Form	2,23	0,97	.89
	English Form	2,53	0,85	

3.2 Construct Validity

3.2.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory factor analysis was undertaken to examine construct validity of the scale and factor loads were calculated for all items. Later, item correlations were investigated to ensure whether the construct was fit for this analysis and it was decided that item correlations were suitable. Sampling adequacy and Bartlett Sphericity tests were done respectively. KMO values need to be higher than .60 for data to be fit for factor analysis and Barlett test should be meaningful (Büyüköztürk, 2003). This study found KMO coefficient as .882 for sampling adequacy and χ^2 value to be 2565.683 for Bartlett Sphericity test ($p < .001$). Results showed that data set was fit for factor analysis.

Statistically, factor load values of 0.40 or higher is a good measurement for selection (Büyüköztürk, 2003). Therefore, factor load value was taken as .40 in this study. Principal Components Analysis and Quartimax rotation methods were used in investigating the factor structure of the scale. The original scale included 6 sub scales.

However, exploratory factor analysis undertaken with the help of Principal Components Analysis did not present the same situation for the sample used in the current study. Examination of scree plot graphic showed that items were collected under five most suitable factors. Eigen value for each factor was above 1. Total variance explained by these five factors was found to be 58.046%. the program automatically disregarded the items that had load values under .40. Load values of the items after factor analysis and their distributions according to sub scales are as follows:

Table 2: Item loads of the scale

	Sub scales				
	1	2	3	4	5
Q29	,799				
Q30	,711				
Q26	,644				
Q28	,615				
Q25	,531				
Q27	,509				
Q22	,468				
Q16		,655			
Q17		,601			
Q20		,572			
Q18		,550			
Q19		,506			
Q9			,680		
Q13			,657		
Q12			,649		
Q14			,593		
Q10			,585		
Q15			,497		
Q11			,415		
Q1				,804	
Q2				,798	
Q7				,532	
Q6				,490	
Q23					,598
Q24					,590

While the original scale that the study was based on included 30 items and 6 sub scales, the construct presented by the sample group was found to have 25 items and 5 sub scales as a result of the exploratory factor analysis. Based on these sub scales and items, confirmatory factor analysis was done.

3.2.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis was undertaken in order to validate the factors obtained according to the results of exploratory factor analysis. Confirmatory factor analysis examined the fit indices of the model and it was seen that chi-square values and goodness-of-fit indices were not at desired levels. Variances in estimate values were

examined and the scale was modified by eliminating the items with extreme variances (a total of five items). The confirmatory factor analysis repeated after item elimination presented that fit values for the model were in acceptable range and the model provided enough evidence that it was structurally fit for “university students”. Table 3 presents the model’s goodness-of-fit values.

Table 3: Goodness-of-fit values for the model

	χ^2	df	χ^2/df	GFI	CFI	IFI	NFI	RMSEA
Goodness-of-fit values	339,125	160	2,11	0,901	0,95	0,92	0,902	0,053
Good fit values*			0--2	$\geq 0,90$	$\geq 0,95$	$\geq 0,95$	$\geq 0,95$	$\leq 0,05$
Acceptable fit values*			02--03	0,89-0,85	$\geq 0,90$	$\geq 0,90$	$\geq 0,90$	0,06-0,08

Path diagram of the model and factor loads are presented in Figure 1.

The scale was finalized with 5 sub scales and 20 items based on the exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses results. Since this scale was different than the original scale and the number of sub scales changed, researchers named the sub scales again. The names and items included in the new version of the sub scales are as follows:

- Leisure interfering with study (strain) = 23-24
- Leisure interfering with study (intensity) = 26,27,28,29,30
- Study interfering with leisure (temporal) = 1, 2, 6
- Study interfering with leisure (strain) = 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15
- Study interfering with leisure (intensity) = 16, 17, 19, 20

3.3 Reliability

Three separate analyses were used to monitor the reliability of the scale. There are methods which are often preferred in reliability analyses. Reliability analyses are undertaken in two ways: Norm-Referenced Test and Methods of Interval Consistency. In the current study, Methods of Interval Consistency methods such as Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient, Guttman reliability coefficient and split-half method were used respectively. Table 4 reports the coefficients for these analyses.

Table 4: Results of reliability analyses for the scale

	Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient	Guttman reliability coefficient (lowest limit)	Split-Half Method
Leisure interfering with study (strain)	0,746	0,373	0,746
Leisure interfering with study (intensity)	0,801	0,633	0,736
Study interfering with leisure (temporal)	0,780	0,494	0,659
Study interfering with leisure (strain)	0,740	0,625	0,703
Study interfering with leisure (intensity)	0,703	0,527	0,716
Whole Scale	0,901	0,751	0,757

As can be observed in Table 4, Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient for the whole scale was found to be 0,901, Guttman reliability coefficient lowest limit was 0,751 and Split-Half Method coefficient was, 757.

Finally, correlation analysis was conducted to investigate the relationship among the sub scales. Table 5 displays the findings for the correlation analysis.

Table 5: Correlation among sub scales

	1	2	3	4	5
Leisure interfering with study (strain)	1	,704**	,513**	,650**	,670**
Leisure interfering with study (intensity)		1	,475**	,632**	,715**
Study interfering with leisure (temporal)			1	,637**	,672**
Study interfering with leisure (strain)				1	,775**
Study interfering with leisure (intensity) (Yoğunluk)					1

4. Discussion and Results

This study aimed to present a new scale to literature by conducting the validity and reliability studies for study-leisure scale.

The total variance explained by the scale was found to be 58.046% according to exploratory factor analysis that was conducted first. Based on literature, values that points to total variance higher than 66% is accepted as a good result, however, it can be claimed that this value is difficult to obtain in practise. Hence, literature in this field reports that total variance over 30% in multiple factor structures can be regarded as significant (Akgül, 2003; Büyüköztürk, 2003; Tavşancıl, 2006; Aksakoğlu, 2001) Also, load values accepted as .32 by some sources (Cokluk et al.,2010) were taken as .40 in this analysis to ensure healthier distribution for the scale items.

Values obtained in the confirmatory factor analysis planned according to exploratory factor analysis showed that the scale had acceptable goodness-of-fit values. Chi-square is an important test conducted in line with confirmatory factor analysis (Bollen, 1989). Values that are below 2 point to perfect fit. The value obtained as a result of the analysis conducted in the current study was 2,11 which is very close to 2 and included in acceptable range.

Additionally, RMSEA value, another indicator of goodness-of-fit for the scale and another sub scale of CFA (confirmatory factor analysis), between .05 and .08 point to good fit and values below .05 show perfect fit (Byrne, 1998; Kelloway, 1998; Hu and Bentler, 1999; Mc Donald and Moon-Ho, 2002; Schmelleh-Engel et al., 2003). This value was found to be 0,053 in the current scale pointing to close proximity to perfect fit. Also, as reported by Marsh et al. (1988), Hu and Bentler (1999) and Schmelleh-Engel et al., (2003), IFI, CFI and NFI values between .90 and .95 show good fit while values higher than .95 point to perfect fit. Meydan and Sesen (2011) reported that perfect fit for GFI values is possible in cases where the value is higher than .90. It was observed in the analyses that two of these values pointed to perfect fit and the other two were close to perfect fit.

In line with reliability analyses, it was seen that coefficients of sub scales changed between .703 and .801 (Cronbach's alpha). Internal constancy coefficients between 0,70 and 0,80 in psychological tests and scales that are prepared to measure a behavior are regarded as an indicator that the tool of measurement is sufficiently usable (Nunnally, 1978). Values over .80 point to very good values for usability (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). According to the results of analysis obtained in the current study, good values were obtained in both Cronbach alpha values and in Split-Half coefficients. Also, total coefficient for the scale was also at a good level with .901. The finding that all sub scales correlated with one another and had high correlation values was evidence that sub scales did not generate differences on their own in the scale.

Findings obtained at the end of the study showed that "Study-Leisure Scale" could be used for Turkish university students. Of course, the study was piloted by the researchers on university students. Future studies can further increase the reliability of the study. In their study on Turkish university students, Gürbüz and Handerson (2014) listed the reasons that generally hindered student participation in leisure activities. The results of this scale can be used to seek answers to questions such as the extent of restrain on participating in leisure activities due to studying or the extent of restrain on concentrating on studies due to participation in leisure activities. This study can also be used to identify which departments had highest conflicts between study and leisure activities and to determine the extent of conflicts between these two concepts to guide departments in recreational terms. Efficiency of university curriculums can also be determined with studies using this scale and other problems can also be addressed by researchers. This scale is also significant as a unique study that can contribute to experimental studies.

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Appendix 1: Study-Leisure Conflict Scale (Turkish Version)

Dersin Boş Zamanla Çatışması (Zamansal)

Ders saatlerim katılmak istediğim boş zaman aktivitesini yapmamı engelliyor.
Boş zaman aktivitelerine katılmak istediğim zamanlarda derse girmek zorunda kalıyorum.
Derslerimden dolayı boş zaman planlarımı değiştirmek zorunda kalıyorum.

Dersin Boş Zamanla Çatışması (Gerilim)

Okuldaki stresli bir günden sonra, boş zaman aktivitesine katılırken en küçük bir şeye bile sinirlenebiliyorum.
Dersten sonra katıldığım boş zaman aktivitelerinde kendimi çok yorgun hissediyorum.
Derslerimle alakalı çok yoğun endişe duyduğum zamanlar boş zaman aktivitemi yapamıyorum.
Okul çevrem beni sinirli ve kaygılı hissettirdiği için boş zaman aktivitelerine katıldığımda bile bir türlü rahatlayamıyorum.
Boş zamanlarım sıklıkla derslerim tarafından engelleniyor ve bu durum beni hem fiziksel hem de mental olarak kötü hissettiriyor.
Okuldaki ortamımdan dolayı, boş zaman aktivitesi sırasında diğer insanlara karşı sinirli davranıyorum.

Dersin Boş Zamanla Çatışması (Yoğunluk)

Derslerimin çok zor olması boş zaman aktivitemi engellemektedir
Derslerimin yoğunluğu boş zaman aktivitelerinde iyi bir beceri sağlamamı engelliyor.
Boş zaman aktivitelerim genellikle çalışma saatlerim tarafından işgal ediliyor.
Derslerimin sorumluluğu boş zaman aktivitelerini yaptığım zamanları engelliyor.

Boş Zamanın Dersle Çatışması (Gerilim)

Boş zaman aktivitesini yaptığım gruptaki gerilim ve kaygı düzeyi, bazen ders aktivitelerimi düzgün yapmada beni zorluyor.
Boş zaman aktivitesini yaptığım gruptaki baskı ve problemler, bazen derslerime konsantre olmam konusunda beni zorluyor.

Boş Zamanın Dersle Çatışması (Yoğunluk)

Boş zaman ihtiyacım o kadar fazla ki derslerimden uzaklaşıyorum.
Boş zaman aktivitelerindeki sorumluluklarımdan dolayı hissettiğim stres derslerime konsantre olmamı zorlaştırıyor.
Boş zaman aktivitesindeki azmimden dolayı, okulda arkadaşlarım benim davranışlarımı kabul etmekte zorlanıyor.
Boş zaman aktivitelerine aşırı katılımımdan dolayı, okulda iyi bir performans göstermekte zorlanıyorum.
Boş zaman aktivitesine gösterdiğim performans ile okulda gösterdiğim performans arasında tamamen bir fark vardır.

Appendix 2: Study-Leisure Conflict Scale (English Version)

Study interfering with leisure (time)

- 1 Class hours interfere with leisure activities I want to participate in.
- 2 I have to be in class during the times I want to participate in leisure activities.
- 6 I have to change my plans regarding leisure due to my classes.

Study interfering with leisure (strain)

- 9 I can get upset about even the smallest things in leisure activities after a stressful day at school.
1
- 0 I feel very tired in leisure activities in which I participate after classes.
1
- 3 When I feel overly anxious about my classes, I cannot do leisure activities
1 I can never relax even in leisure activities since my school environment makes me feel anxious and
4 tense.
1 My classes often interfere with my leisure time and this makes me feel bad both physically and

1 mentally.

1

5 I act tense during leisure activities because of the school atmosphere.

Study interfering with leisure (intensity)

1

6 The fact that my classes are difficult interferes with my leisure activities

1

7 Intensity of my classes stops me from obtaining good skills in leisure activities

1

9 My leisure activities are generally invaded by study hours

2

0 Responsibility in classes interferes with the periods I participate in leisure activities.

Leisure interfering with study (strain)

2 Level of tension and anxiety in the group in which I participate in leisure time activities sometimes interferes with my performance in classroom.

2 Pressure and problems in the group in which I participate in leisure time activities, sometimes interferes with my concentration in classes.

Leisure interfering with study (intensity)

2

6 I have such a high need for leisure that I withdraw from my studies.

2 The stress I feel as a result of the responsibilities in leisure activities makes it hard for me to concentrate.

2 Due to my determination in leisure activities, friends at school are having a hard time accepting my behaviors.

2 I am having difficulty in performing well at school because of intense participation in leisure activities.

3

0 There is complete difference between my performance in leisure activities and at school.

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